

A P O L L O

D2.1: Report on User Requirements

WP2 – Users' needs analysis and specifications

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Executive summary

Aim of this deliverable was to define the requirements, from the user perspective, for completing APOLLO main objective which is the development of a commercial platform that will provide a suite of farm management advisory services, specifically designed to address the needs of small farmers.

At the beginning, an analysis of APOLLO platform competitors was made. In total, 14 different commercial platforms were analysed for exporting their specifications and for identifying APOLLO platform positioning and competitive advantages.

Research interviews with farmers and agricultural consultants were followed and focus group discussions were employed for elicitation of user's requirements. Questions included, among others: the IT infrastructure that is available to farmers, the kind of information they require from the platform, the way that they prefer to interact with the platform, etc. For reaching a critical mass of responses, the consortium took advantage of its own networks and links. In total, 140 farmers and 25 crop consultants were participated.

The collected data, were analysed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques for ensuring the precision, reliability and integrity of the results. Outcome of this procedure was the definition of the exact user requirements for each one of the services provided by APOLLO platform.

The results were document in form of "Personas" and "Scenarios Of Use" for delivering a more comprehensive view by enhancing realism and for offering insights into the ways that the platform will be actually used.

1 User Requirements: General Perspective

The aim of this deliverable was to define the requirements, from the user perspective, for completing APOLLO main objective, which is the development of a commercial platform that will provide a suite of farm management advisory services, specifically designed to address the needs of small farmers.

The success of a project like APOLLO depends crucially on capturing the user perspectives in order to develop a platform that will be fully integrated into existing business processes and processing chains. The users in APOLLO project have been defined to be the farmers, agricultural cooperatives and crop consultants. The goal of this study was to understand the needs of potential end-users mainly in terms of the type of information they require, their preferred interaction with the platform, the interfaces and the functionalities.

This research work was conducted at the three pilot sites of APOLLO project (Greece, Serbia and Spain), with the contribution of APOLLO end-users main target groups (small farmers, agricultural consultants and agricultural cooperatives). This study is essential to support the definition of Services Specifications (Task 2.2) as well as the Co-Creation of Services (Task 2.3). In addition, the results will be used for the platform development and integration (WP5) and the exploitation and communication (WP7).

1.1 User requirements

User requirements can be defined as a property that must be exhibited in order to solve a problem of the real world to satisfy specific target group (Sawyer and Kotonya, 2001). There are different levels and types of software requirements like business requirements, business rules, constraints, external interface requirements, features, functional requirements, nonfunctional requirements, quality attributes, system requirements and user requirements (Wiegiers and Beatty, 2013). Maiden (2008), defined system requirements as the desirable system property which, when implemented, will lead to the achievement of at least one user requirement.

User-centered design is the design process in which end-users influence the final design (Abrams et al., 2004) and its usage can increase usefulness and usability of the final products (Vredenburg et al., 2002). Participatory design process is the process where the roles of the designer and the researcher interact as the user becomes the critical component (Sanders, 2003). The difference between user-centered design and participatory design approaches is that the former was constructed for the user, while the latter with the user (Sanders, 2003). Kujala (2003) referred both to the qualitative and quantitative benefits of user involvement in the product design process such as improved quality of the system, avoidance of costly system features, improved levels of acceptance, greater understanding of the system, increased participation in decision-making, increased sales, decreased user support, decreased training costs and increased productivity. On the contrary, he also mentioned obstacles from the user involvement such as user motivation and user awareness about design process and designers' needs.

In total, there are three different software development methodologies: Waterfall; Iterative and Agile. Each methodology has its own advantages and disadvantages (Wiegiers and Beatty, 2013). Waterfall models are sequential models and they are the most common models in software development history. Key characteristic of Waterfall method is the positioning of the development phases at the

sequence of their execution and its main disadvantage is the inflexibility of divisioning the development activities (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Waterfall software development process.

On the other hand, Iterative methodology (Figure 2) surpasses Waterfall disadvantages. Iterative method introduced interactions between end-users and prototype versions of the software. These interactions aim to refine the software in order to fully meet users requirements. However, this approach also has disadvantages such as: the high probability of failure in replacing the prototype with the final solution, compromises at the expense of software quality, resources cannot be accurately assessed.

Figure 2 – Iterative software development process.

Agile methodology (Figure 3) alleviates some of the obstacles associated with the previous two methodologies. Its aim is to shorten the time period between the decision making process and the feedback gained from the beta users. Using Agile method, the unique abilities of each project participant are highlighted, making specific, complex and change intensive projects successful (Matkovic and Tumbas, 2010).

Figure 3 - Agile software development process.

Mitchell et al. (2009) found that Iterative method is superior compared to Waterfall method. Specifically, they found that the Iterative method requires more effort in general than the Waterfall method, but this effort is less in requirements elicitation and more in testing. As a result, programmers are more productive and they are developing higher quality products. In addition, Rico (2008) found that Return Of Investment (ROI) using Agile method was four times higher than the other methods. However, the above mentioned methods presents differences at the goals that they fulfil: Waterfall and Iterative methodologies were developed for optimizing productivity and quality, while Agile methodology was developed for optimizing speed, satisfaction, project success and ROI.

Figure 4 - The distribution of effort spent for each one of the main software development methodologies.

A basic process taking place during Agile development stage is the user requirements analysis. User requirements analysis aims on the identification of the tasks and the goals of end-users within a given product or idea (Wiegiers and Beatty, 2013).

In this study, user requirements were conducted based on the methodology proposed by Maguire and Bevan (2002) and Wiegiers and Beatty (2013) (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - General process for user requirements analysis.

More specifically, for carrying out the user requirements analysis, sequential steps were followed based on Maguire (2001) eliciting user requirements steps in a human-centered design. These steps were:

- Key Stakeholder Profiles
- Competitor Analysis
- Task Mapping
- User Requirements Interviews
- Focus Groups
- Personas
- Scenarios Of Use

Key Stakeholder Profiles identified APOLLO platform's stakeholder groups (*Information Gathering*); Competitor Analysis gathered information about the services offered from APOLLO platform's competitors (*Information Gathering*); Task Mapping identified for each APOLLO proposed service, the usages of APOLLO platform at different crops and cultivation systems (*Requirements Specification*); User Requirements Interviews were essential for understanding farmers and crop consultants needs along with the importance of APOLLO offered services (*User Needs Identification*); Focus groups were beneficial for enabling a better - in depth view of the interviews results (*User Needs Identification*); Personas delivered a more comprehensive view by enhancing realism and increasing engagement of the APOLLO platform's design team with end-users representations and (*Envisioning And Evaluation*); Scenarios Of Use provided a view of APOLLO platform by offering insights into the ways that the platform will be actually used (*Envisioning And Evaluation*).

Identification of APOLLO platform's user requirements was a phenomenological research study and for this reason, qualitative approaches were used for analysing the data. Phenomenological studies are powerful to understand subjective experience, gain insights into people's motivations and actions and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. In design, qualitative approaches are used in order to explore and identify new ideas and innovative insights that can be part of the design of new products and services (Lester, 1999).

1.1.1 Key Stakeholder Profiles

Maguire (2001) described stakeholder analysis as the analysis that identifies, for each user and target group, their main roles, responsibilities and task goals in relation to the system. APOLLO's main stakeholders were identified during proposal phase by assessing their priority interests. In total, three stakeholder profiles were identified. These are the small farmers, the agricultural cooperatives and the agricultural consultants.

The definition of a "**small farmer**" depends on the context that is going to be used. Small-size agricultural holdings are characterised by distinctive common measurable features, such as the utilised agricultural area (UAA), the amount of labour input, the level of self-consumption and the economic size of the farm. For the context of Earth Observation science and related services the absolute physical size of the farm, commonly characterised by the number of hectares of UAA. By applying this criterion, small farmers are often defined as those farmers having less than 2 or less than 5 hectares of UAA (European Commission, 2011). These farmers account for 67.4% of the EU-28's UAA (Coyette and Schenk, 2013). Consequently, small farmers have a significant role in being more efficient producers in labour-surplus economies, in helping contain poverty, on preventing premature urban migration and in ensuring a degree of food security. However, most small farmers are not able to achieve a good income due to rapid changes in commodity markets and they have limited access to technologies that can help them increase their production (IFPRI, 2005).

Agricultural cooperatives enabling the self-provisioning of economic actors with goods and services whose delivery is precluded by the constraints on the social division of labour. Agricultural cooperatives are controlling a 50% share in the supply of agricultural inputs (Tortia et al., 2013). According to FAO¹ agricultural cooperatives' role is to facilitate small farmer's access to:

- Natural resources
- Information, communication and knowledge
- Markets, food and productive assets
- Policy- and decision-making

In this way, agricultural cooperatives is shown to overcome the limitations that are produced by small farmer's inability to realize economies of scale (Valentinov, 2007). Since they federate the interests of a group of farms, they are an important stakeholder group for the APOLLO platform development either as a direct customer in and of themselves, or as a multiplier through which individual farms could be targeted.

Agricultural consultants provide advisory services to farmers. Their role can be identical to agricultural cooperatives or supplementary to the services that are provided by agricultural cooperatives. According to Coutts et al. (2007) agricultural consultants may provide various services such as:

¹ <http://www.fao.org/docrep/016/ap431e/ap431e.pdf>

- Agronomic advice (technical, bug checking, spray management, nutrition, water management, yield mapping, variety choice, planting schedules)
- Farm business planning and implementation
- Economics and management decision making
- Benchmarking training

Moreover, additional stakeholders of APOLLO platform can be:

- Farmer's Unions, Councils and Federations
- Producers' organizations and Unions of Producers
- Chambers of Agriculture and Chambers of Agronomists
- Enterprises

1.1.2 Competitor Analysis

Competitor Analysis can provide valuable information about the extent to which current systems meet user needs and can identify potential usability problems to avoid in the new system (Maguire and Bevan, 2002). In addition, it contributes on investigating and identifying the pricing policies, the system's positioning, the competitive advantages and the communication strategy (Bergen and Peteraf, 2002). The most common method for identifying user requirements from competitor analysis is through product online reviews (Jin et al., 2016).

For the purposes of this deliverable, a thorough online market research was conducted for mapping the competitors of APOLLO platform and for identifying user requirements through their market position. Research projects were also evaluated for having a better understanding of future trends in EO based agriculture platforms. Table 1 contains a small description of the competitive, to the APOLLO platform, services as well as their market strategies.

Table 1 – Competitor platforms description summary

COMPETITOR PLATFORMS	DESCRIPTION
FARMSTAR	FARMSTAR ² is a satellite technology-based service devised and delivered by Airbus Defence and Space since 2003. FARMSTAR's users are taking advice on precision agro-management knowing the exact time and area where they should apply fertilizer and pesticides. Satellites flying over the fields take accurate measurements of the radiant solar energy absorbed and reflected from the surface across the farm terrain. The value of the reflected energy varies according to the level of growth of the vegetation, thus satellite measurements can indicate crucial field factors such as soil moisture, surface temperature, leaf cover and level of chlorophyll. Personalised "recommendation cards" divided into very small areas of the field are provided to each user, offering her/him prescriptions for the necessary amounts of chemicals that should be applied, as well as where and when to be applied. The FARMSTAR service provides its subscribers the opportunity for a better environmental, economic and social management. The average price for FARMSTAR services to the farmer is €10/ha, generating approximately €4,4 million in turnover for Astrium Services in 2011. By 2011, coverage was 440.000 hectares and 10.000 farmers had subscribed to it.

² <https://www.farmstar-conseil.fr/>

PIXAGRI	Terranis' PIXAGRI ³ is a decision support tool for farmers based on remotely sensed data which allows detection of sub- and inter-field variations for optimising the application of agricultural inputs. It is a generic product suite based on optical satellite imagery allowing farmers to identify and control the agronomic factors of their yield. Aimed primarily at farmer's cooperatives, PIXAGRI is available for all types of crops and is most suitable to large areas (+2000 ha). The product suite is comprised of agriculture maps over the territory, analysis of yielding capacities in a region as well as heterogeneity and vigour maps. It is sold as a service that delivers maps providing crop status information and is commercialized through a yearly subscription over a fixed territory. The price is 5 to 10 €/ha/year, depending on the level of information required. Currently, TerraNIS commercialises the PIXAGRI product range in Midi-Pyrenees (France), Canada, Hungary, Serbia, other regions in France (via Airbus Defence and Space).
SOYLSense	SOYLSense ⁴ uses satellite imagery to measure crop canopy variations. Leaf Area Index (LAI) maps with information of the requirements of nitrogen application are produced based on the data obtained, allowing the optimization of nitrogen rates. SOYLSense enables farmers to monitor their field and acquire advices about the application of nitrogen fertilizers. Moreover, users can view their LAI map online and have the ability to create and process their own nitrogen application maps.
TalkingFields	Started as an ESA-led project, TalkingFields ⁵ is an operational cost-effective Precision Farming service, combining GNSS technologies with Earth Observation (EO). For a terrain located using Navigation Technologies, the user requests a specific service from the TalkingField's catalogue, such as the "Improved Soil Mapping", the "Economic Evaluation" or the "Yield Estimation". Based on navigation information, EO measurements and land surface modelling, the provider prepares the custom made service and offers users recommendations for individual farm treatment, application of cost-effective practices and more effective farming systems.
HydroBio	HydroBio ⁶ provides farmers with an irrigation decision support system using weather and Earth Observation data to estimate the precise water needs of each field along with crop monitoring. HydroBio users receive information that enables them to deliver an optimal irrigation strategy to their field including maps for the previous days water use, recommended irrigation schedules, strategies to meet irrigation deficit when necessary, information about the best applied practices and what needs to be improved.
PiMapping®	eLEAF's PiMapping ⁷ (Pixel Intelligence Mapping) Technology uses satellite imagery, weather information and precipitation data to create "smart pixel" images providing information about cropped surfaces and enabling the development of applications for the agricultural sector. It provides to farmers information such as growth, moisture and yield for almost all cropped surfaces, and offers them the ability to better manage their irrigation practices by delivering daily data about their crop's actual evapotranspiration, biomass production and crop water requirements.
CropLook	CropLook ⁸ informs farmers with potatoes and wheat crops about their crop growth in a weekly basis, offering them growth parameters such as crop evaporation, nitrogen content, and yield figures. CropLook using remote sensing, while the satellite information is being processed with the ETLook algorithm for being translated into crop data.

³ <http://terranis.fr/en/pixagri/>

⁴ <http://www.soyl.com/index.php/services/soylsense>

⁵ www.talkingfields.org

⁶ <http://hydrobioars.com/>

⁷ www.eleaf.com/technology-pimapping

⁸ www.croplook.com/

GrapeLook	GrapeLook ⁹ project, is based on satellite technologies (earth observation, satellite communication and navigation) as well as terrestrial technologies, and aims to help grape farmers with the irrigation water resources and nitrogen applications in the Western Cape, South Africa. All data obtained, such as soil moisture levels; irrigation retrieval from evapotranspiration updates; and digital boundaries of vineyard blocks, were uploaded on the project website, which were publicly accessible. Moreover, farmers received an irrigation forecasting tool and a SMS/MMS service with information on irrigation scheduling and fertilizer application.
FruitLook	FruitLook ¹⁰ , a successor of GrapeLook, covers a larger area of crops including deciduous fruit trees. Weekly data on crop's growth, water use and nitrogen content are available to farmers for free. In the near future, the developers of FruitLook will release an "irrigation planner" which will inform farmers about when, where and how much they should irrigate to avoid water stress in their crops.
The Pastures from Space	The Pastures from Space ¹¹ project aims to deliver near real-time information tools at a whole-farm and within-paddock level of forage crop production. The Pastures from Space provides estimates of pasture production during the growing season by means of remote sensing. Satellite data is used to accurately and quantitatively estimate Pasture Biomass or Feed On Offer (FOO) or combined with climate and soil data is used to produce Pasture Growth Rate (PGR) estimates.
URSULA Agriculture	URSULA Agriculture ¹² provides a suite of services based on imagery from drones, aircraft and satellites. Products include Ursula Crop Performance (a crop monitoring service which measures within field variation across the growing season), URSULA Scout (a rapid mapping and quantification tool for highlighting areas of crop stress), URSULA Trials (a quantitative comparison tool enabling the evaluation of agricultural trials), URSULA Farm View (aerial imaging tool enabling visual assessment of crop progress) and URSULA Compliance (a service aimed at supporting CAP subsidy claims).
Irrisat	Irrisat ¹³ is a research project that is focused on providing information on irrigation needs to the farmers and Irrigation User Associations based on Earth Observation satellites. Except of irrigation related information offers crop vigor information along with meteorological data.
Oenoview®	Oenoview® ¹⁴ is an innovative remote sensing tool that produces a cartography of vineyards. This information is used by viticulturists in order to apply site specific management at their vineyards and monitor them at sub parcel level.
AGRIVI	AGRIVI ¹⁵ is a platform that offers complete farm management. It has the ability to monitor weather and provide alerts on crop pests and diseases. Also, offers tools for crop management, farm economics, resources and inventory and growing analytics and reports.

All the aforementioned information was summarized in terms of offered products, sources used for data acquisition, imagery resolution, target crops, services coverage and target groups (Table 2). Mapping of the offered products by APOLLO platform's competitors was conducted for getting a clearer view on what type of information should APOLLO platform provide on its users and potentially diversify from other competitors. Therefore, the products offered were clearly stated and the data

⁹ <https://artes-apps.esa.int/projects/grapelook>

¹⁰ www.fruitlook.co.za/

¹¹ www.pasturesfromspace.csiro.au/

¹² www.ursula-agriculture.com/

¹³ <http://www.irrisat.it/>

¹⁴ <http://www.icv.fr/en/viticulture-oenology-consulting/oenoview>

¹⁵ <http://www.agrivi.com/farm-management-software/>

sources were investigated, due to the fact that the quality of information provided by these platforms is related to the usage of alternative data sources (e.g. images from drones). For instance, optical satellite images are constrained by the presence of clouds during image acquisition. For overcoming this, image acquisition approaches using drones and manned aircrafts are applied (Gago et al. 2015). Moreover, the imagery resolution has been specified, as it is necessary for some specific agricultural practices, and the target crops for each one of the competitor platforms have been highlighted.

Consequently, based on their specifications, comparisons between APOLLO and its competitors were conducted (Tables 3, 4 and 5). Table 3, shows an extensive comparison between the products/services offered from each one of APOLLO's competitors. The products were clustered in seven categories, based on the services that APOLLO platform is going to offer (tillage scheduling, irrigation scheduling, crop growth monitoring and yield estimation) along with other products/services that competitors are offering (i.e. fertilization service and alerts on pests and diseases). In Table 4, the technical specifications of each solution (Data Sources, Offered Imagery Resolution and Region Coverage) were highlighted, while in Table 5, the target groups and the crop types supported by each platform were analysed.

Table 2 – Competitor platforms specifications summary

COMPETITOR PLATFORMS	PRODUCTS	DATA SOURCES	IMAGERY RESOLUTION	EST. YEAR	CROPS	COVERAGE	TARGET GROUPS
FARMSTAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal nitrogen application maps • Optimal spraying dates • Forecasts on the maturity date • Information and maps about the state of the crops • Alerts on Diseases • Estimate of yield prediction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites • Manned Aircrafts • Drones 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >0.05 m (with aerial imagery) • >0.5 m (satellite imagery) 	2002	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wheat • Barley • Maize • Rapeseed • Sugar beet 	Worldwide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural cooperatives • Public Chambers of Agriculture • Farmers' groups • Private companies • Subcontracting companies • Local public authorities
PIXAGRI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop development maps • Sub-field zoning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	2 m	2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any crop 	Worldwide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives • Consultants • Industry players • Seed suppliers • Institutional agencies
SOYLsense	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal nitrogen application maps • Crop monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites • Drones 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >0.2 m (with aerial imagery) • > 1 m (satellite imagery) 	2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Winter wheat • Winter oilseed rape • Winter barley • Oats 	Europe Africa Oceania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives

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COMPETITOR PLATFORMS	PRODUCTS	DATA SOURCES	IMAGERY RESOLUTION	EST. YEAR	CROPS	COVERAGE	TARGET GROUPS
TalkingFields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persistent relative fertility maps Management zones maps Biomass maps Yield maps Yield forecast maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellites 	>20 m	2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Winter wheat Winter barley Rapeseed Sugar beet Maize 	Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Agricultural cooperatives Consultants
HydroBio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation related maps Crop monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellites 	>3 m	2012	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any crop 	Worldwide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Agricultural cooperatives Consultants
PiMapping®	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biomass production CO2-intake Leaf Area Surface Actual evapotranspiration Nitrogen Yield of different crops Water productivity score Crop water requirements Meteorological parameters Crop monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellites 	>20 m (or higher resolution due to better satellites)	2011	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any crop 	Worldwide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Agricultural cooperatives Consultants Industry players Policy makers Governments
CropLook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yield Dry matter Total biomass production Crop growth information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellites 	>20 m (or higher resolution due to better satellites)	2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potatoes Maize Sugar beet Wheat Sugarcane 	Worldwide (Europe, Africa)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Agricultural cooperatives Consultants

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COMPETITOR PLATFORMS	PRODUCTS	DATA SOURCES	IMAGERY RESOLUTION	EST. YEAR	CROPS	COVERAGE	TARGET GROUPS
GrapeLook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomass production • Leaf Area Index • Vegetation Index • Evapotranspiration (actual and deficit) • Biomass Water Use Efficiency • Nitrogen in leaf • Nitrogen in upper leaf layer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	>20 m (or higher resolution due to better satellites)	2011	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wine grapes 	Worldwide (Africa)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives • Consultants
FruitLook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomass production • Leaf Area Index • Vegetation Index • Evapotranspiration (actual and deficit) • Biomass Water Use Efficiency • Nitrogen in leaf • Nitrogen in upper leaf layer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	>20 m (or higher resolution due to better satellites)	2011	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plums • Peaches • Pears • Table grapes • Wine grapes • Apples 	Worldwide (Africa)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives • Consultants • Industry players • Policy makers • Governments
The Pastures from Space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feed on offer • Pasture growth rate • Total dry matter • Greenness imagery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	30 m	2004	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pastures 	Australia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives • Consultants
URSULA Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop monitoring • Optimized inputs application • Informed drilling and planting strategies • Early yield estimates • Weed monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites • Manned Aircrafts • Drones 	>0.01 m (with aerial imagery) 5 – 10 m (satellite imagery)	2011	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any crop 	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Consultants • Trial companies

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COMPETITOR PLATFORMS	PRODUCTS	DATA SOURCES	IMAGERY RESOLUTION	EST. YEAR	CROPS	COVERAGE	TARGET GROUPS
Irrisat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of irrigation requirements • Crop monitoring • Weather forecast • Registration of irrigations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	20 m	2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any crop 	Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers
Oenoview®	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fertilization maps • Young vineyards sites maps • Botrytis prone area maps • Crop vigor maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites 	2 m	2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wine grapes 	Worldwide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wine growers • Cooperative wineries • Consultants

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Table 3 – Survey on offered products by competitor

	TILLAGE SCHEDULING PRODUCTS	IRRIGATION SCHEDULING PRODUCTS	CROP GROWTH MONITORING PRODUCTS	FERTILIZATION PRODUCTS	ALERTS ON PESTS AND DISEASES	YIELD ESTIMATION PRODUCTS	METEO PRODUCTS
FARMSTAR			X	X	X	X	
PIXAGRI			X				
SOYLSense			X	X			
TalkingFields			X			X	
HydroBio		X	X				
PiMapping®		X	X				X
CropLook			X			X	
GrapeLook		X	X				X
FruitLook		X	X				X
The Pastures from Space			X			X	
URSULA Agriculture	X		X	X		X	
Irrisat		X	X				X
Oenoview®			X	X	X		
APOLLO	X	X	X			X	X

Table 4 – Survey on technical specifications by competitor

	DATA SOURCES			IMAGERY RESOLUTION			GLOBAL COVERAGE
	Satellites	Manned Aircraft	Drones	<1 m	1 – 10 m	10 – 30 m	
FARMSTAR	X	X	X	X	X		X
PIXAGRI	X				X		X
SOYLSense	X		X	X	X	X	
TalkingFields	X					X	
HydroBio	X				X		X
PiMapping®	X					X	X
CropLook	X					X	X
GrapeLook	X					X	X
FruitLook	X					X	X
The Pastures from Space	X					X	
URSULA Agriculture	X	X	X	X	X		
Irrisat	X				X	X	
Oenoview®	X				X		X
APOLLO	X					X	X

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Table 5 – Survey on crop type and target groups by competitor

	CROP TYPES		TARGET GROUPS					
	Arable	Grapes and Orchards	Farmers	Cooperatives	Crop Consultants	Industry	Policy Makers	Government
FARMSTAR	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
PIXAGRI	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SOYLSense	X		X	X	X			
TalkingFields	X		X	X	X			
HydroBio	X	X	X	X	X			
PiMapping®	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
CropLook	X		X	X	X			
GrapeLook		X	X	X	X			
FruitLook		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
The Pastures from Space	X		X	X	X			
URSULA Agriculture	X	X	X		X	X		
Irrisat	X	X	X					
Oenoview®		X	X	X	X			
APOLLO	X		X	X	X			

From the tables above, it is clear that different products are currently available to farmers at different crops. Specifically, the products that are offered to farmers and other stakeholders of the agricultural sector provide information regarding (i) crop growth parameters (e.g. vigor, leaf area, biomass), (ii) weather conditions (e.g. evapotranspiration, weather forecast), (iii) crop nutritional status and requirements (e.g. leaf nitrogen, optimal nitrogen application maps), (iv) water use and requirements (e.g. water use efficiency, irrigation doses), (v) pests and diseases alerts (e.g. botrytis prone area maps) and (vi) yield (e.g. yield forecasts, yield estimations).

It is worth mentioning that most of the competitors, are using only satellite data while there are a few companies that currently using data acquired from other sources (manned aircrafts and drones). These companies have the ability to offer products that demand higher resolution (e.g. weed detection) compared to satellite data. It also needs to be highlighted that most of APOLLO's platform competitors are using more than one satellite constellations for providing better results on their products.

Most of platforms are offering products/services for one or more arable crops (e.g. Farmstar, TalkingFields) while only one is offering products/services for a number of orchard crops (FruitLook). Moreover, there are two products focusing on wine grape production (GrapeLook and Oenoview®) due to the specific characteristics of this crop (i.e. high specialization and high correlation between grape and wine quality). There are also platforms offering products for every crop (e.g. PIXAGRI and HydroBio), but these platforms provide limited information which is usually focused on crop monitoring and irrigation scheduling.

Finally, most of the competitors are focused on providing products/services for farmers, agricultural cooperatives and agricultural consultants. However, some of the competitors have acknowledged other target groups for their platforms such as trial companies, industry players, policy makers and governments.

Competitor Analysis results showed that the uniqueness of APOLLO platform is its ability to define tillage scheduling based on satellite imagery. Moreover, APOLLO platform is one of the few platforms that could provide enhanced irrigation scheduling. However, for increasing APOLLO competitiveness, the integration of fertilization services, pest alerting services and data acquisition mechanism from additional sources (i.e. drones and manned aircrafts) should be investigated.

1.1.3 Task mapping

Observation methods used for checking the amount of time spent on various activities, for observing events that interviewees may be unable or unwilling to share and for observing situations that interviewees have described. Goal of this method is to help researchers to develop a holistic understanding of the phenomena under study (Kawilich, 2005). Many studies have identified the benefits gained by using observation for eliciting user requirements (Nuseibeh and Easterbrook, 2000; Faily and Flechais, 2010; Rehman et al., 2013).

For the needs of this study, observation methods were used for getting a better understanding of the field operations that the farmers make during a crop period as well as their frequency. A document named Crop Calendar was circulated before the interview survey to the APOLLO project pilot partners (ACP, UPOR and AgriSat) in order to fill it in (Annex I). This document contained questions regarding the time and type of field operations taking place in a crop period. Each partner completed the form according to the crops that they are interested in, and the results of this research are shown in Table 6.

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Table 6 - Crop Calendars for the crops under study

● Tillage Scheduling Service, ● Irrigation Scheduling Service, ● Crop Growth Monitoring Service, ● Crop Yield Estimation Service

COUNTRY	CROP	MONTH											
		January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
GREECE	Winter Wheat	●	●	●			●		●		●	●	
	Cotton	●	●	●	●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	● ●	●	●	●	
SERBIA	Barley		●	●		●		● ●		●	●		
	Maize				●	● ●				●	● ●		
	Soya			●	●	● ●				●	●		
	Sugar Beet			●	●	● ●	●		●	●	● ●		
	Sunflower			●	●	● ●			●	●	●		
	Winter Wheat		●	●		●		● ●			●		
SPAIN	Almond Trees			●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	●			
	Chinese Garlic	● ●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	● ●	●			●	●	●	
	Maize			●	● ●	● ●	● ●	● ●	●	●	●	●	
	Olive Trees		●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	● ●	● ●	●		
	Purple Garlic	●	●	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	●	●				●	●
	Vineyard			● ● ●	●	● ● ●	● ●	● ●	● ● ●	●			
	Winter Wheat		●	●	●	●		●			●		●

In addition, a qualitative data analysis for identifying the frequency of field operations carried out during a crop period was conducted. For the analysis, ATLAS.it data analysis software (ATLAS.ti GmbH, Berlin, Germany) was used and the operations that are taking place during a crop period were clustered based on APOLLO's offered services. The analysis results are shown in Figure 6 in form of a wordcloud where bigger and bolder words represents the operations referred more times by the pilot site partners.

Figure 6 - Wordcloud with the field operations taking place in a crop period. Bigger and bolder words represents the operations referred more times by the pilot site partners.

Tillage and spraying operations presented the highest frequency among the three pilot sites independently of the crop. Moreover, task mapping analysis showed that the crop is correlated with the frequency and time of operations (Table 6) justifying the need for providing services according to these parameters. Furthermore, it needs to be mentioned that the frequency and time period of the offered services are different for the same crop among different countries. This has to do with the different weather conditions along with the different agricultural practices that are followed by farmers in each country. For example, farmers that apply conservation agriculture may not plow the soil at all. On the other hand, farmers that follow more intensive agriculture have higher number of operations in a year (e.g. Spain).

1.1.4 User Requirements Interviews

As mentioned above, user requirements elicitation can include different methods which require interaction with stakeholders. The most common method for user requirements elicitation is personal interviews. Interviews are offering an in depth view, which makes them useful for qualitative studies. In modern user requirements elicitation there is a mixed method approach where questionnaires and interviews are used together for eliciting important information (Harris and Brown, 2010). A lot of researchers from different disciplines, pinpoint the benefits of using interviews during their studies (Atkinson et al., 2004; Klemick et al., 2015; Pattison et al., 2015; James et al., 2016; Henrich et al., 2016; Middleton et al., 2016). Personal interviews can be divided into three categories according to how open or close the questions are. These are the structured interviews, the semi-structured interviews and the unstructured interviews. Structured interviews include closed type questions with multiple choice answers, semi-structured interviews include questions with a mix of predefined answers and open answers, while the unstructured interviews have only open questions that the interviewee can answer in whatever way he/she likes (Burnay et al., 2014).

APOLLO platform's requirements elicitation process was faced as a phenomenological research. For this reason, a semi-structured interview survey was followed for eliciting user requirements of the two main stakeholders (farmers and crop consultants) with the usage of the appropriate questionnaires (Annex II and Annex III). Agricultural consultants provide services working on their own or under an organization such as agricultural cooperatives. Consequently, they are closely related to the farmers who are the main stakeholders of APOLLO platform's services. The interview survey took place at the three pilot sites of the APOLLO project (Giannitsa - Greece, Ruma - Serbia

and Castilla-La Mancha – Spain) during June and July 2016. The questionnaires were divided into four main sections. The first section was the demographics, where information related to the age and education of the interviewees was assessed. The second section was related with crop practices. Specifically, it included information on crop cultivation or support according to the interviewee (farmer or crop consultant) and technologies that are incorporated at farm level. The third section was referred to the importance, according to their needs, of the agricultural services that are going to be offered by APOLLO platform. The fourth section included questions related to APOLLO’s platform implementation such as spatial information level, refresh rate (temporal resolution) of the data, ways of interaction between end-users and the platform, ways of payment, etc. At the end of every questionnaire, there was a closed question regarding the intention of the interviewees to test APOLLO platform for assessing their interest.

The analysis of the results was conducted using both quantitative and qualitative analysis software. Specifically, SPSS 23 (IBM Inc., New York, USA) was used for the statistical analysis of the closed questions of the interviews providing a quantitative analysis, while the open questions were analysed using ATLAS.ti 7 (ATLAS.ti GmbH, Berlin, Germany) software. The answers of each interview per country were combined in order to achieve homogenized qualitative analysis, since the APOLLO platform will implement a unified marketing infiltration strategy for covering the needs of every European farmer.

1.1.4.1 Farmers

The first set of questions included information related to demographics. A summary of the participants’ demographics can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7 - Average demographics and cultivation area per country (farmers).

Country	Farmers	Age Group*	Education*	Cultivation Area*
Greece	36	45-54	Secondary	< 10 ha
Serbia	51	35-44	Secondary	10 – 30 ha
Spain	34	45-54	Secondary	10 – 30 ha
	121	45-54	Secondary	10 – 30 ha

*It refers to the answer with the highest frequency.

Figure 7 - Farmers education level (%).

Figure 8 - Type of crops cultivated by farmers (%).

A large number of farmers has received basic education (Figure 7), and the farm sizes (60.3%) are less than 30 ha (Table 7). They mainly cultivate arable crops (72.6%) and orchards (50%), while 26.4% of the farmers cultivate vegetables (Figure 8). About 57.7% of farmers answered that they were familiar with the use of desktop PCs and 46.3% with smartphones for having access to the internet. However, a significant number of the respondents (20%) didn't have any access to the internet (Figure 9). About 59.3% of the farmers answered that they have knowledge in using maps in their daily life (Table 8). A 95.7% of the farmers stated that precision agriculture is quite important nowadays, while 95.5% stated the importance of using satellite data in agriculture. However, a large number of the interviewees answered that they do not currently use these kinds of systems (65.3%), but they intent to use them in the future. Greek and Serbian farmers are not using Smart Agricultural Technologies (> 80%). On the contrary, almost 80% of the Spanish farmers are using these type of technologies (Table 9). A large number of farmers that currently uses smart agriculture technologies and practices answered that they are familiar with applications regarding weather forecast while few of them answered that have used sensors, GPS receivers or satellite based tools.

Figure 9 – Devices used by farmers' for accessing internet.

Table 8 – Usage of map based applications (Farmers).

	GREECE	SERBIA	SPAIN	TOTAL
YES	41.7 %	80.4 %	50 %	59.3 %
NO	58.3 %	19.6 %	50 %	40.7 %

Figure 10 – Importance of smart agriculture according to farmers.

Figure 11 – Importance of satellite data in agriculture according to farmers.

Table 9 – Smart agriculture technologies usage by country (Farmers).

	GREECE	SERBIA	SPAIN
Users of Smart Agriculture Technology	16.7 %	17.6 %	79.4 %
Non Users of Smart Agriculture Technology	83.3 %	82.4 %	20.6 %

A large number of farmers found that the services that will be offered by APOLLO platform are very important and useful to their daily activities. Most of the farmers participated in the survey mentioned that the products of the tillage scheduling service (soil workability and soil moisture variation) are very important and they should have knowledge on them (Figure 12).

Figure 12 - Importance of tillage scheduling products according to farmers.

Most of the farmers answered that the irrigation scheduling service is very helpful, mentioning that the most important information that can be provided from this service is the amount and the time of irrigation (Figure 13).

Figure 13 - Importance of irrigation scheduling products according to farmers.

Regarding the crop growth monitoring service, farmers found most useful to retrieve information about crop stage and vigor variation. However, information such as biomass variation and leaf area variation was also mentioned as quite important to them (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Importance of crop growth monitoring products according to farmers.

Above 60% of the farmers wants to have estimations of crop yield and quality before harvest, while less than 40% of them wants to have information related with residue yield (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Importance of yield estimation products according to farmers.

Some of the farmers expressed the opinion that APOLLO platform should be enhanced with additional products. These products should provide information regarding weather forecast and weather conditions, and alerts for pest and diseases.

Figure 16 - Importance of different types of data visualization according to farmers.

Farmers found very useful the ability of APOLLO platform to send different types of alerts. Primarily they expressed preference on having notification through SMS (33.3%) and via the APOLLO platform (16.3%) and secondly via email (13%). However, 32.5% of them answered that they would like to have the ability to receive alerts in more than one ways. Preferably, they would like to receive the various alerts directly and as a second choice via their crop consultant. Moreover, they found very important the capability to have different types of data visualization such as maps, charts, statistics and reports (Figure 16). Some respondents suggested that there should be access to historical data and recommendations on crop practices. Additionally, the data should be exported in appropriate data formats such as pdf, csv, shapefiles and text, while many of them annotated that the information must be given in an easy and understandable way. Farmers answered that it would be useful to be able to interact with other farmers and crop consultants. According to 70.2% of farmers' responses, farmers must be able to change the alerting levels according to their needs.

Regarding the pricing policy, farmers mentioned that they are willing to pay for APOLLO platform services only if the APOLLO platform is affordable and provide reliable and cost effective results. Additionally, APOLLO platform should follow a flexible market policy such as pay on demand and according to the use (43.8% of the respondents answered this), while they found interesting to have the ability to choose the services that they want to get information from (85.1% of the respondents).

The interviewees were interested in receiving the information in different resolutions such as information per field, per management zone and per crop. Most of the farmers didn't want to have the ability to change the service algorithms provided by the APOLLO platform (57%), due to their inability to understand the science behind them. However, a small number of farmers wanted to have this ability for using more optimized algorithms for their local conditions. Finally, farmers highlighted the importance of the APOLLO platform as a complementary tool for improving their crop production and efficiency. For this reason most of the respondent farmers are willing to try APOLLO platform and to participate in the development phase.

Table 10 – Summary of answers from farmers related to the APOLLO platform implementation.

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS
Importance of different type of alerts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMS (33.3 %) • EMAIL (13 %) • APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (16.3 %) • SMS & EMAIL (8.1 %) • SMS & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (8.1 %) • EMAIL & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (5.7 %) • SMS & EMAIL & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (10.6 %) • OTHER (Letter & Phone Call) (4.9 %)
Ways of receiving information from the APOLLO platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directly (68.3 %) • Through Crop Consultant (31.7 %)
Importance of different ways of visualization of information	Data projection in form of maps (59.3 %) and reports (52 %) was preferred
File types export	Data and reports must be exported in PDF and CSV formats
Need for historical data	87% of the farmers wants to have access in historical data
Frequency of information communication	Most of the farmers (36.5%) wants to receive updated data every week
Interaction with other farmers	87.8% of the farmers wants to interact with other farmers via APOLLO platform
Interaction with crop consultants	90.2% of the farmers wants to interact with crop consultants via APOLLO platform
Change of alert levels	70.2% of the farmers wants to be able to change APOLLO platform's alert levels
Reason for changing the alert levels	Different seasonal needs of crops due to different crop stage and better optimization of APOLLO services based on their experience
Will for paying for the APOLLO platform	Many farmers (37.4%) expressed the will to pay for APOLLO platform only if it will affordable and will provide reliable and cost effective results
APOLLO platform payment model	Most of the farmers (43.1%) wants a flexible payment model for paying APOLLO platform (e.g. according the number of services and period of use)
Ability on choosing APOLLO platform services	Most of the farmers (88.6%) wants to be able to choose which services they are going to use
Ability on having management zones information per field	Most of the farmers (84.6 %) wants to have information based on different management zones
Granularity of information	50.4% of the farmers wants to receive information per field while 19.5% and 13.8% of the farmers wants to receive information regarding the different management zones and per hectare (ha) respectively. Some of them wants to receive information per crop and per location

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS
Ability on creating custom algorithms	Most of the farmers (57%) don't want to have the ability to create custom algorithms.
Contribution of the APOLLO platform to farmer's current cultivation practices	Most farmers answered that APOLLO platform services are going to help them on increasing their efficiency and their profitability

1.1.4.2 Crop Consultants

The first set of questions included information related to demographics. A summary of the participants' demographics is shown in Table 11.

Table 11 - Average demographics and cultivation area per country (crop consultants).

Country	Crop Consultants	Age Group*	Education*	Cultivation Area*
Greece	7	18-34	Graduate	300 - 600 ha
Serbia	7	35-44	Graduate	> 900 ha
Spain	6	35-44	Graduate	600 – 900 ha
	20	35-44	Graduate	300-600 ha

*It refers to the answer with the highest frequency.

All the interviewees-crop consultants hold bachelor degrees. Most of them belongs to a relative young age group (35-44) making them quite familiar with new technologies. They are connecting to the internet via desktop PCs and smartphones (85%) and they are familiar with the use of maps (95%). They are quite skilled in agronomy as they are providing crop advices regarding different types of crops (arable crops and orchards mainly). They are usually advising less than 200 farmers (85%) on pests and diseases controlling and on farm operations scheduling. Many of them combine the advisory services that they offer to their clients with crop protection products reselling. Moreover, they are clearly understanding the importance of using smart technologies and satellite data in agriculture (Figure 17). However, few of them (20%) are currently using these technologies for providing better advices to their farmers.

Figure 17 - Importance of satellite data and smart technologies in agriculture (Crop consultants).

A large number of crop consultants found that APOLLO platform will enhance their advisory services. Most of them mentioned that the products of the tillage scheduling service (soil workability and soil moisture variation) are very important (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - Importance of tillage scheduling products according to crop consultants.

Most of the them answered that the irrigation scheduling service is very helpful, mentioning that the most important information that can be provided from this service is the amount and the time of irrigation (Figure 19).

Figure 19 - Importance of irrigation scheduling products according to crop consultants.

Regarding the crop growth monitoring service, most of crop consultants mentioned that crop growth monitoring service is the most useful for them. They found very useful to know information regarding crop vigor variation and the crop stage (Figure 20).

Figure 20 - Importance of crop growth monitoring products according to crop consultants.

Above the 50% of the crop consultants answered that is very important to have estimations of crop yield and product quality before harvest (Figure 21).

Figure 21 - Importance of yield estimation products according to crop consultants.

In addition, they suggested that products related with weather forecast and weather conditions, water profile and soil nutrients concentration must be developed for increasing APOLLO’s platform efficiency. Crop consultants mentioned that the alerts created by the APOLLO platform must be visible via the APOLLO platform app and SMS. The data must be projected in the form of reports, maps, statistics and charts (Figure 22), and must be able to be exported in different formats such as pdf, shapefile, text and csv.

Figure 22 - Importance of different type of data visualization according to crop consultants.

As in farmers case, crop consultants found very useful to ability to communicate with other APOLLO users (farmers and crop consultants). Crop consultants wants to be able to change the alerting levels (75%) for receiving the necessary for them information at each crop stage, and they want to be able to customize services algorithms according to their needs. They are willing to pay for a platform like APOLLO (65%), but a 35% expressed the opinion that they will pay for it only if the offered advices are credible and the prices are reasonable. In addition, according to 55% of crop consultants, APOLLO platform needs to follow a flexible subscription model as they want to pay on demand according to the number of services they will use and the frequency of their usage. Finally, most of the crop consultants want to receive a trial version of the APOLLO platform due to their strong belief that a platform like this can improve the efficiency of the advisory services that they are providing to their customers.

Table 12 - Summary of answers from crop consultants related with the APOLLO platform implementation

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS
Importance of different type of alerts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMS (20 %) • EMAIL (5 %) • APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (30 %) • SMS & EMAIL (5 %) • SMS & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (10 %) • EMAIL & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (20 %) • SMS & EMAIL & APOLLO APP NOTIFICATIONS (10 %)
Importance of different ways of visualization of information	All of the proposed visualization methods are important
File types export	Data and reports must be exported in PDF, SHP and CSV formats
Need for historical data	95% of the crop consultants wants to have access in historical data of their clients
Frequency of information communication	Most of the crop consultants (40%) wants the data to be updated weekly
Interaction with farmers	95% of the crop consultants wants to interact with farmers through APOLLO platform
Interaction with other crop consultants	90% of the crop consultants wants to interact with other crop consultants
Change of alert levels	75% of the crop consultants wants to be able to change APOLLO's alerting levels
Reason for changing the alert levels	Different seasonal needs of crops due to different crop stage and better optimization of APOLLO services based on their experience
Will for paying for the APOLLO platform	Many crop consultants (35%) expressed the opinion that they will pay for APOLLO platform only if the offered services are credible and the prices are reasonable

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS
APOLLO platform payment model	Most of the crop consultants (55%) wants a flexible payment model for paying APOLLO platform according to the period and the number of used services
Ability on choosing APOLLO platform services	Most of the crop consultants (80%) wants to be able to choose which services they are going to use
Ability on having management zones information per field	Most of the crop consultants (95%) wants to have information based on different management zones
Granularity of information	45% of the crop consultants wants to receive information per field while 20% and 20% of them wants to receive information regarding the different management zones and per hectare (ha) respectively. Few of them wants to receive information per crop and per location
Ability on creating custom algorithms	Most of the crop consultants (75%) don't want to have the ability to create custom algorithms. The other 25%, believes that by creating custom algorithms can adapt APOLLO platform better to their needs
Contribution of the APOLLO platform to crop consultant's current cultivation practices	Most crop consultants mentioned that APOLLO platform services can help them provide more accurate and efficient advices to their clients

1.1.5 Focus Groups

Focus Groups is a popular qualitative method for eliciting user requirements. Focus groups as the other qualitative research methods offers insights into the question of “why” people do particular things or present a specific behaviour (Rosenthal, 2016). The reason for this is that engages participants in an efficient way for conducting an in-depth analysis (Carrey, 2015). Focus groups are guided and directed by a moderator but they are driven by the participants and can provide in depth analysis by the interaction between experts. Moreover, it was found that can solicit the ideas of these experts in a short period of time compared to individual interviews (Sutton and Arnold, 2013). Finally, many researchers proved that focus groups can offer in depth analysis by engaging small number of people with different field areas of research (Bruseberg and McDonagh-Philp, 2002; Easton et al., 2003; Kelin et al., 2007; Warholak et al., 2011; Yager et al., 2013; Dixon et al., 2016; May et al., 2016).

In total, three focus group surveys (one for each pilot site) were conducted for the purposes of this deliverable. These groups consisted of famers and crop consultants and the topics discussed were:

- Current crop production problems
- Practices that followed for facing these problems
- Prospects given from APOLLO platform for facing these problems
- APOLLO's platform implementation
- Temporal resolution (refresh rate) of the provided data
- APOLLO's platform information flow
- The market infiltration model that APOLLO platform should adopt

Aim of the focus groups surveys was to get a clearer view on the answers that were received during interviews. Focus groups survey guidelines can be seen in Annex IV. At first, each participant filled a questionnaire related with his education level, his age and his profession. Focus groups answers were coded in an excel file and a qualitative analysis per topic was made using ATLAS.ti 7. The answers of each focus group were combined in order to achieve a homogenized qualitative analysis since the APOLLO platform will implement a unified marketing infiltration strategy for covering the needs of every European farmer.

The demographics of the focus groups surveys showed that participants were experienced in agriculture, but there was a big difference in the education level between Spanish participants and the participants from the other 2 countries.

Table 13 - Average demographics of the focus groups surveys.

Country	Farmers	Farmers Education*	Crop Consultants	Crop Consultants Education*	Age Group*
Greece	5	Secondary	3	Graduate	45-54
Serbia	10	Secondary	1	Graduate	45-54
Spain	4	Post Graduate	1	Post Graduate	45-54
	19	Secondary	5	Graduate	45-54

*It refers to the answer with the highest frequency.

The participants firstly referred to the crop production problems that they are facing during the cultivation period (**Topic I**). Large number of them referred to the lack of proper information (e.g. weather forecast, soil moisture) and knowledge for facing problems such as irrigation scheduling, fertilization and pest management, as they currently cultivate according to their personal experience. Also, they mentioned that they need this information on time while the technologically advanced farmers added that this information must be available in a high resolution level.

Secondly, they referred on how they solve these problems (**Topic II**). Participants from Greece and Serbia answered that due to lack of information, in most cases they rely on their own experience and on the crop consultants' experience using crop scouting methods. They indicated that sometimes are using data from sensors and weather forecasts. The Spanish farmers, that being more technologically advanced compared to the others (according to sampled individuals), referred that they are solving the problems using their crop consultants' services that are available to them which including satellite crop scouting.

After this, participants were asked about the expectations that they have from the APOLLO platform (**Topic III**). The participants referred to the need of having historical data and information that is accurate and on time. This information must be related to weather forecast (e.g. precipitation), fertilization, spraying, harvest and irrigation. Preferably, this information must be provided daily while there must be an option of exporting it for utilizing it in precision agriculture equipment, as task file.

Focus groups participants discussed also the way APOLLO platform should be developed regarding the information provided (**Topic IV**). They mentioned that different data formats (e.g. maps, full reports) on different devices (smartphones, desktop PCs, tablets) must be supported. Moreover, they highlighted the need of an easy to use interface for its users while the information should have different spatial resolution to meet each farmer's technological state.

Temporal resolution (**Topic V**) should be according to crop development and the type of information (service). For example, irrigation scheduling should be on daily basis. Other participants suggested that there should be weekly information available for every service.

Consequently, focus groups participants referred on how this information should be available to them (**Topic VI**). The farmers highlighted the fact that this information must be interpreted by their crop consultants under protocols of collaboration. The platform should also provide the ability to communicate with other farmers and crop consultants. Crop consultants and farmers agreed that they must have information related to crop growth for a larger area than their fields even if it is not so accurate. In this way, they will have a more clear view on what may affect positively or negatively their crop's growth.

Finally, participants mentioned that the APOLLO platform's users should have the ability to test it before purchasing a subscription (**Topic VII**). Also, the APOLLO platform should follow a pay per service and pay per use marketing strategy. In addition, APOLLO platform must be easy to use and must provide accurate information compared to the tools that are currently used for achieving a reasonable market infiltration.

1.1.6 Personas

Personas are descriptive models of archetypal users derived from user research. They are formed using characteristics of people who present similar goals, motivations and behaviours. They have a supportive role in order to describe and highlight differences between goals and behaviours (Saffer, 2007). Consequently, they enhance realism and increase engagement in a design team with end user representations (Marshall et al., 2015). There are two different types of personas according to Pruitt and Adlin (2006). These are the data driven personas and the assumption driven personas. Data driven personas are based on research results and have high credibility compared to the assumption driven personas that are usually used when there is a constrained time period to collect and analyse data. Personas proved their use on user requirements elicitation process in many cases and in adverse professions for capturing conceptual models (LeRouge et al., 2013; Sim and Brouse, 2014; Vincent and Blandford, 2014; Sim and Brouse, 2015). However, this method like other presents its own constraints. Specifically, personas aren't used as often as expected in the software design process in which they were firstly introduced, while from the research side there have been questions whether they substitute real users with personas (Matthews et al, 2012; Bodker et al., 2012). Designers may not use personas, but use a process based on their own opinions or stories relating to interactions with a product according to Friess (2010) while marketing and sales professionals will not use this when they already know their clients priorities (Ronkko et al, 2004).

For the APOLLO project's user requirements elicitation purposes six different personas were developed. The personas were based on the data that were collected during the interviews and focus groups surveys. Data such as age, education, crop type cultivations, area of cultivation, devices for accessing the internet, familiarity with maps applications, smart farming technologies usage level and crop challenges (e.g. irrigation problems, pests and diseases problems, etc.) were used for developing each country's Persona that was assigned as farmer. On the other hand, information such as age, education, advisory services area, type of cultivations for advisory services, devices

for accessing the internet, smart farming advisory level and advisory challenges were used for developing each country's Persona that was assigned as crop consultant. These data were analysed for behavioral characteristics which were incorporated in the personas. As a result there were three farmers and three crop consultants Personas. Internet images were used for visualizing the Personas. The images used are under creative commons licenses for using them freely in this document.

(Thodoris Papadopoulos)

Farmer in Soybean Field by UnitedSoybeanBoard (2008)
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/unitedsoybean/9624213286/>
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Occupation: Farmer

Age: 50

Crops: Cotton, Wheat

Cultivation Area: 8 ha

Nationality: Greek

Thodoris is a third generation farmer in Giannitsa, Greece. Like his father he cultivates arable crops and specifically cotton and wheat. He is also a farmer member on the Agricultural Cooperative of Pella (ACP).

Thodoris has seen his income decreasing. His crop expenses are getting larger while the international commodity values are remaining stable each year.

He uses his computer and TV to get informed on weather forecast and he gets advices from ACP's crop consultants and other neighbor farmers when a problem arises. He is going every day to his fields for crop scouting in order to address problems such as pests and diseases immediately.

He is thinking to move on smart farming for increasing his profits but his is not sure how.

Goals

- Save time and money
- Income increase
- Move to smart farming
- Become better farmer

Motivations

- Environmental friendly
- Adopt new farming practices

Frustrations

- There is lack of knowledge on new technologies and practices in the area
- There are limited data regarding the weather conditions

Technology Skills

Crop Challenges

Smart Farming Level

(Vasilis Alexiou)

Young Farmer Robbie Emerson by LEADelaware (2013)
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/leadelaware/11354975493/>
 Attribution (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/>)
 Photo Attribution by PhotosForClass.com

Occupation: Crop Consultant

Age: 34

Crops: Arable Crops and Orchards

Advisory Area: 210 ha

Nationality: Greek

Vasilis is a crop consultant in Giannitsa, Greece. He holds a degree in Agronomy. He is a second generation agronomist in the area and he is specialized in arable crops and orchards. He manages a crop supplies shop for farmers on his own.

He uses his computer and smartphone to support his advices to farmers. However, it is extremely difficult for him to monitor all the fields of his clients.

For this reason he wants to use new and innovative crop advisory services tools. Vasilis believes that smart farming technologies is an area that he also needs to specialize. This will help him to expand his offered services for enhancing his firm around the region and for increasing the number of his clients.

Until now the solutions that he tried offered limited information and services while the user interface was too complicated.

Goals

- Save time and money
- Income increase
- Move to smart farming
- Expand his services
- Expand his reputation

Motivations

- Become better crop consultant
- Learn and support new farming practices

Frustrations

- The current solutions are too complicated and offer limited information

Technology Skills ● ● ● ○ ○

Advisory Challenges ● ● ● ● ○

Smart Farming Level ● ● ● ○ ○

(Slobodan Petrović)

William Dawson Gunter on a tractor – Live Oak by State Library and Archives of Florida (1955)
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/floridamemory/16007587645/>
 No known copyright restrictions (<http://flickr.com/commons/usage/>)
 Photo Attribution by PhotosForClass.com

Occupation: Farmer

Age: 34

Crops: Maize, Barley, Wheat, Soya

Crop Area: 11 ha

Nationality: Serbian

Slobodan is a second generation farmer in Ruma, Serbia. Like his father he cultivates arable crops and specifically maize, soya, barley and wheat. He is also a farmer member of the Association of farmers of the Municipality of Ruma (UPOR).

Slobodan faces a lot of problems with the weather conditions. He doesn't know the optimal time for cultivating and spraying his fields. Currently, everything he is doing is based on his own experience.

He uses his computer and smartphone to get informed on weather forecast while he uses additional sources of information (e.g. crop diseases databases) for improving his knowledge.

He is thinking to use a system that will provide him with better weather forecasts and will alert him about the optimal timing for performing agricultural operations like tillage and sowing in his fields. He heard that UPOR will use a satellite based system for crop monitoring and he is willing to give it a try.

Goals

- Save time and money
- Income increase
- Become better farmer
- Move to smart farming

Motivations

- On time agricultural operations
- Adopt new farming practices

Frustrations

- There is lack of knowledge on new technologies and practices in the area
- The weather forecast is not so accurate for his region

Technology Skills

Crop Challenges

Smart Farming Level

(Goran Marić)

Farmer Adem by adem80 (2010) <https://www.flickr.com/photos/adem/4255831433/>
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 Photo Attribution by PhotosForClass.com

Goran is an experienced agronomist that has recently hired from an agricultural cooperative in Ruma, Serbia. He holds a bachelor degree in Agronomy and has been working as an agronomist for 15 years.

Goran understands that agricultural cooperative's members face a lot of problems due to the unpredictable weather. He currently uses his PC and smartphone to access information related to the local weather forecast for addressing possible crop problems that may occur.

He is thinking of using a system that will help him to monitor the fields of all the members of the agricultural cooperative that he is working. This system needs to be able to provide him with accurate and on time alerts on crop monitoring problems and soil workability.

Occupation: Crop Consultant

Age: 40

Crops: Arable Crops

Advisory Area: 920 ha

Nationality: Serbian

Goals	Motivations	Frustrations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient crop monitoring Become better crop consultant Expand agricultural cooperative's services to its members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer proper agricultural services Learn and support new farming practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current solutions offer limited information while they are quite expensive

Technology Skills ● ● ● ○ ○

Crop Challenges ● ● ● ● ○

Smart Farming Level ● ● ● ○ ○

(Juan Carlos García)

Farmer Scouting & Inspecting Weeds by UnitedSoybeanBoard (2013)
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/unitedsoybean/13782778215/>
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 Photo Attribution by PhotoForClass.com

Juan Carlos is an experienced and innovative farmer in Castilla-La Mancha, Spain. He cultivates garlic, maize and winegrapes. He moved to smart farming practices with the support of a crop services company of his area. He uses variable rate technology for applying pesticides and fertilizers. Juan Carlos uses smartphone and PC to access information related with weather forecast and crop monitoring from data available by private and public sector organizations. However, he finds that the level of services that receives regarding crop monitoring and irrigation is insufficient compared to the money he spends. So, he wants to try a solution more efficient and cheaper than the one that uses right now.

Farmer Scouting & Inspecting Weeds by UnitedSoybeanBoard (2013)
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/unitedsoybean/13782778215/>
 Attribution (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/>)
 Photo Attribution by PhotoForClass.com

Occupation: Farmer

Age: 48

Crops: Garlic, Maize and Wine grapes

Advisory Area: 230 ha

Nationality: Spanish

Goals	Motivations	Frustrations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Income increase Become better farmer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Become more efficient Adopt new farming practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current solutions are quite expensive and offer little

Technology Skills ● ● ● ○ ○

Crop Challenges ● ● ● ● ○

Smart Farming Level ● ● ● ● ○

(Maria Sánchez)

Maria is an experienced and innovative crop consultant in Castilla-La Mancha, Spain. She works on a private company that offers precision agriculture solutions and services. Among the services that her company offers are prescription maps for variable rate fertilization, variable pesticide application as well as crop yield estimation. In order to support their services, they use a network of sensors that is established across their clients' farms. These sensors include weather stations and soil moisture sensors. However, this approach is quite expensive for her company. For this reason, she wants to try a less expensive approach using high resolution satellite data.

Wheat Field Love by Solly Markovitch (2008) <https://www.flickr.com/photos/28280729@N05/2849526535/>
 Attribution (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/>)
 Photo Attribution by PhotosForClass.com

Occupation: Crop Consultant

Age: 44

Crops: Arable Crops and Orchards

Advisory Area: 750 ha

Nationality: Spanish

Goals	Motivations	Frustrations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient and cheap crop monitoring Offer more accurate services Become better crop consultant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Become more efficient Adopt more accurate farming practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The current solutions are quite expensive and offer little efficiency

Technology Skills ● ● ● ● ○

Crop Challenges ● ● ● ● ●

Smart Farming Level ● ● ● ● ●

1.1.7 Scenarios

According to Suri and March (2000), scenarios are descriptions of natural, constructed or imagined contexts for user-product interactions. Nardi (1992) defines scenarios as a description of a set of users, a context and a set of tasks that users perform or want to perform. Scenario-based design focuses on describing how users accomplish tasks whereas in the persona-scenarios approach the user is presented as a particular person with emotions, actions and needs and the person is the focal point and not the system (Madsen and Nielsen, 2010). Client narratives provide a pragmatic view of the information system, offering insight into the ways the system is actually used and the habitual practices of the work environment (Alvarez and Urla, 2002). Scenarios / storytelling methods have been used in interdisciplinary areas for enhancing the ability of stakeholders to understand characteristics and competencies through unique experiences and background when it is not available (Davidson, 2004).

For the needs of this research, Personas based scenarios method was used for eliciting user requirements. The six Personas were developed according to characteristics derived from the questionnaires and the focus group survey. For each Persona farmer, one scenario was assigned while for each crop consultant Persona two scenarios were assigned. Main reason for this choice was the fact that crop consultant's daily tasks meets more and adverse challenges compared to the farmer's daily tasks.

Scenario 1

Irrigation Scheduling on Cotton Crop

Information Needs: Needs to know when and how much to irrigate in order to achieve the maximum crop yield and quality without wasting water

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for weather forecast, soil moisture and irrigation dose

Timeliness: Daily information on soil moisture, irrigation dose when it is needed, weather forecast

Extend of Information: SMS alerts, charts and graphs, reports with service results, forum with APOLLO users

Thodoris Papadopoulos has established a cotton crop in April. It was a rainy period that helped his crop to emerge. However, now that the weather is quite dry, he considers irrigation to help his crop's growth.

He began to use the APOLLO platform recently when one of his friends suggested it to him. He is a bit cautious on using it. He has only purchased the irrigation service (parcel level) to give it a try. For this reason, he uses the communication tool within the platform to get more feedback on the APOLLO's irrigation scheduling service. There are farmers and crop consultants that have already tested this service and share their experiences with him. They have encouraged him to trust APOLLO platform's irrigation scheduling service.

He consults the irrigation scheduling service to retrieve information regarding soil moisture level and irrigation dose. He is also able to see this information in charts and maps. He is starting to feel sure for his choice to subscribe to APOLLO platform's irrigation scheduling service.

After two months of irrigation scheduling service trial, Thodoris seems quite glad for his choice. He is sure that he saves enough money and water on irrigation. He is quite impressed from the fact that the irrigation dose is adapted according to each crop stage and from the fact that receives SMS alerts from the platform.

It is one week after cotton harvest. Thodoris's cotton production was higher than expected although he used less water due to the combination of irrigation doses and accurate weather forecasts from the APOLLO platform's service. He can see this in the final report that is generated from the APOLLO platform based on the service selection. He wants to encourage other farmers to use this service also. He communicates his results to the APOLLO platform users. Next year he is thinking of purchasing the crop growth monitoring and yield estimation services.

Scenario 2

Crop Growth Monitoring in Giannitsa

Information Needs: Needs to monitor important crop parameters (e.g. crop vigor and crop stage) for many fields of different ownership in order to define crop growth abnormalities

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for crop vigor and crop stages of wheat

Timeliness: Daily information on crop vigor, crop vigor accumulation rate, crop stage

Extend of Information: Reports on crop vigor service, multiple fields monitoring

Vasilis Alexiou has recently subscribed to the APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring service. He wants to monitor the crop growth of his important clients and to provide this information to them as test users of this service.

After receiving information from other APOLLO users and reading the service description manual on the offered service he understands what to expect from the APOLLO platform. At this stage LAI and Biomass are not so important for him. He is more concerned on the crop vigor's accumulation rate. He has inserted in the system the fields that he is more interested in.

After one month of use, he is happy for his choice. Now, he can monitor the crucial crop stages as well as the crop stages changes. Two weeks ago, Vasilis received alerts from the crop growth monitoring service due to low accumulation rate of crop vigor in wheat crops. He went at his clients fields to find out the reason. Vasilis discovered that it was fungi infestation at an early level. He suggested to his clients to spray with a fungicide.

Three months have passed since this incident and wheat crops have been harvested. A severe fungi outbreak was occurred. All farmers have met severe yield loss except of Vasilis's clients. Their on time spraying with fungicide helped them to prevent the infestation.

He has done the right choice by subscribing to APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring. He has saved important time on crop scouting. Even his clients are quite impressed with the detailed reports that Vasilis generated from the APOLLO platform. He is going to expand his offered services with irrigation scheduling and yield estimation services and he decided that he will also provide the Biomass and LAI information to his clients.

Scenario 3 Cotton Variety Adaptability Assessment

Information Needs: Needs to monitor important crop parameters (e.g. crop vigor, LAI and crop stage) for many different crop varieties in order to compare them and find the best suited varieties for his clients' fields

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for weather data (accumulated growing degree days, temperature and precipitation), crop vigor, biomass accumulation, LAI and yield

Timeliness: Daily data recording on weather data (accumulated growing degree days, temperature and precipitation), crop vigor, biomass accumulation, LAI and yield

Extend of Information: Charts, maps, statistics and reports from multiple fields with comparison. Export data in pdf and csv format.

Vasilis Alexiou wants to sell only the best cotton varieties to his clients. For doing this, he needs to assess adaptability of different cotton varieties in his region. He is going to do this using the APOLLO platform.

APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring service will help him to see the effect of different cotton varieties on important indices such as crop vigor, biomass accumulation, LAI and other.

He is also going to use APOLLO platform's weather tool for comparing crop growth with important climate parameters such as growing degree days, temperature and precipitation.

The yield estimation service will assess the final yield for judging the cotton variety adaptability in the climate conditions of Giannitsa.

All these data are going to be exported at his office from the APOLLO platform in useful file formats such as csv and pdf. Charts, maps, statistics and reports will help him to decide which cotton varieties should suggest to his clients.

Scenario 4 Tillage Scheduling in Ruma

Information Needs: Needs to identify the time when the best or appropriate soil moisture conditions for tillage operations are met

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for soil moisture levels and soil workability and soil workability forecast

Timeliness: Daily alerts and notification on soil moisture for tillage operations and for certain time

Extend of Information: Alerts and notifications from smartphone app

Slobodan Petrović is concerned about the tillage operations that take place at his fields. He faced a lot of problems during previous years. The most serious problems included his tractor stuck in the mud and a later seeding that didn't allow him to harvest on time because of bad weather conditions.

This year, Slobodan is going to use the APOLLO platform's tillage scheduling service. He is going to test it on his spring crops related tillage operations from March to May before taking the decision to subscribe to other services.

After one month of trials, Slobodan finds the APOLLO platform easy to use. He receives alerts and notifications on his smartphone via the APOLLO platform app.

Slobodan has just finished sowing of his spring crops. The weather was abnormally wet but this didn't affect him doing his field operations compared to his neighbors. At previous years he was thinking to invest on bigger tractor and implements for making on time his tillage operations. Now he understands that having useful information is more important and quite cheaper than this option. He is going to expand his subscription to the other services also.

Scenario 5 Yield Estimation in Ruma

Information Needs: Needs to know crop yield parameters (crop yield, crop quality and crop residue yield) before harvest in order to arrange harvest operations and crop residue management

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for crop yield, quality and crop residue yield

Timeliness: Before harvest estimation of yield, quality and crop residue yield

Extend of Information: Report on crop yield estimation service results for many fields

Goran Marić and the agricultural cooperative that he works for, are concerned with the barley yield. The crop conditions aren't so good while the time of harvest is coming. The agricultural cooperative needs to estimate yield and yield quality for the fields of its members in order to better plan their logistics.

Goran is responsible for this process. He is going to try the APOLLO platform's yield estimation service to assess yield and yield quality of the barley production.

APOLLO platform allows him to organize the barley harvest campaign. When the first trucks with barley seed arrive in the agricultural cooperative, he checks yield and quality parameters with the ones that yield estimation service provided. He expresses his admiration on how well APOLLO platform's yield estimation service estimated barley's yield and quality parameters. This gave him the chance to organize better barley harvest and storage.

Goran through the crop residue subservice found that if the agricultural cooperative collect barley's crop residues then it will have a good supplementary income. He also stated that this service could optimize the logistics of additional crops expect barley.

Scenario 6 Fertilization Optimization in Ruma

Information Needs: Needs to know important crop growth information for arranging fertilization and to be able to export this information in data formats for calculating fertilization doses with other software

Required Accuracy: Parcel level information for weather data, crop vigor and crop stage

Timeliness: Daily monitoring of crop vigor and crop stages

Extend of Information: Monitoring on crop growth monitoring service, export data in csv format, connectivity of exported data files with other software

Goran Marić and the agricultural cooperative that he works for, wants to offer better fertilization advices to farmers. For achieving this, they will use APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring service.

Crop growth monitoring service offer monitoring on important crop parameters as well as monitoring in changes of crop stages. Goran will use this information for arranging the fertilization schedule. At the same time, he is going to use crop vigor information for calculating the fertilization doses per field. Goran will do this by exporting the desired data in a csv file. Then he is going to import the data in another software for calculating fertilization doses per crop and per crop vigor.

In this way, Goran succeeded to help the agricultural cooperatives members to save money by applying proper fertilization. Many of them observed yield increase despite using less fertilizers. Next year, Goran is thinking of using this information in crop spraying along with other information derived from the APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring service like LAI.

Scenario 7

Selective Harvesting in Castilla-La Mancha

Information Needs: Needs to estimate crop yield per management zones for assessing crop profitability and arranging selective harvest

Required Accuracy: Management zones level information for crop yield and quality

Timeliness: Before harvest estimation of yield and quality

Extend of Information: Comparison of crop yield estimation service between different management zones with charts and maps, Export maps in shapefile format

Juan Carlos García has subscribed recently in crop growth monitoring and yield estimation service of the APOLLO platform for using it on garlic crop. Currently, he has a contract for giving his garlic production to a local garlic processing unit. He is going to be paid according to the grade of the garlic production he delivers. He is aware that if he harvest uniformly then he is going to have less income due to the heterogeneity his fields present. For this reason he is thinking of trying selective harvesting in garlic.

He will use the management zones maps from the APOLLO platform for harvesting. The management zones will be created according to crop parameters and the yield estimation service. As a result he is going to have a complete report with charts and maps on the estimated yield and quality per management zone. He compares the proposed selective harvest with a uniform harvest. He understands that he will succeed more profit by conducting selective harvest so he will give it a try.

Just before harvest, Juan Carlos connects to the APOLLO platform for extracting the maps with the management zones according to garlic bulb size in shapefile format. At the garlic processing unit he understands that his calculations were true. If he was following a uniform harvest he would lose 1000 € per ha. APOLLO platform helped him to increase his income. He is going to share his story with other APOLLO platform users in the forum.

Scenario 8

Variable Rate Prescription Maps in Castilla-La Mancha

Information Needs: Needs to be able to use different spectral vegetation indices than the ones provided in APOLLO and export this information in high resolution

Required Accuracy: 0.1 ha level information of user based spectral vegetation indices

Timeliness: Daily information

Extend of Information: Export maps of user based spectral vegetation indices

Maria Sánchez wants to offer cheap and efficient variable rate prescription maps to her customers using precision agriculture technologies. For this reason she has subscribed to the APOLLO platform's crop growth monitoring service (0.1 ha resolution).

She wants to assess a different spectral vegetation index for monitoring crop growth from the ones provided by APOLLO platform. So, she gets access to the APOLLO platform model builder to insert her spectral vegetation index. Then she uses

this to generate maps for her clients.

She is going to export the maps from the APOLLO platform for interpreting them in prescription maps. She is going to implement her own algorithms for this.

After the variable rate applications, Maria compares APOLLO platform with other competitor products. She realizes that she achieves better results with less money. Additionally, she notices the APOLLO platform's suite is more user friendly and more flexible.

Scenario 9

Region level Crop Monitoring in Castilla-La Mancha

Information Needs: Needs to provide tillage scheduling, irrigation scheduling, crop growth monitoring and crop yield estimation services in different spatial resolution and different alert levels to her clients

Required Accuracy: Parcel, management zones and 0.1 ha level information for soil moisture, soil moisture variation, soil workability, crop vigor, crop vigor accumulation, biomass, biomass accumulation, LAI, crop yield, quality and crop residue yield

Timeliness: Daily information for tillage and irrigation scheduling and crop growth monitoring services and before harvest information on crop yield estimation service

Extend of Information: Change alert levels of the different services, use different resolution and information frequency according to user needs, shared access to services between farmers and crop consultants

Maria Sánchez and the company she works for, are thinking to have centralized crop monitoring for their clients' fields. For this reason they are going to use all the services of the APOLLO platform. They are going to use different resolution and different information frequency according to crop stage.

Moreover, they are going to change the alert levels according to their clients' needs. Their knowledge on their clients' farms can support them to do this properly. The access to client's data is granted by their clients who have the ability to change their status.

In this way, Maria and her company can provide homogenized services to all clients.

2 User Requirements for the APOLLO platform

2.1 Sign in / Profile Page

User Requirement	Users Feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Profile picture	4	4
Customization of profile	4	4
Set language preference (default to language of entry point)	5	5
View posts and contributions via profile page	3	4
Remember log in credentials for quicker log-in	5	5
Access APOLLO platform via PC, tablet and smartphone using browser and mobile apps	5	5

2.2 APOLLO platform Services

2.2.1 Tillage Scheduling Service

User Requirement	Users Feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Soil moisture current state	3	5
Soil workability current state	5	5
Soil moisture forecast	3	5
Soil workability forecast	5	5
Current weather conditions	4	5
Weather forecast	5	5
Tillage scheduling service (Level of detail: Parcel Level)	5	5
Tillage scheduling service (Level of detail: Management Zones)	4	5
Tillage scheduling service (Level of detail: 0.1 ha)	2	5

2.2.2 Irrigation Scheduling Service

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Soil moisture current state	4	5
Time of Irrigation	5	5
Irrigation Dose	5	5
Soil moisture forecast	3	5

Irrigation Dose forecast	3	5
Current weather conditions	4	5
Weather forecast	5	5
Irrigation Scheduling service (Level of detail: Parcel Level)	5	5
Irrigation Scheduling service (Level of detail: Management Zones)	4	5
Irrigation Scheduling service (Level of detail: 0.1 ha)	2	5

2.2.3 Crop Growth Monitoring Service

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Crop stages	4	5
Crop vigor	5	5
Crop vigor accumulation	5	5
Crop stage forecast	4	5
Biomass	3	5
Biomass accumulation	3	5
Current weather conditions	4	5
Weather forecast	5	5
Crop Growth Monitoring service (Level of detail: Parcel Level)	5	5
Crop Growth Monitoring service (Level of detail: Management Zones)	4	5
Crop Growth Monitoring service (Level of detail: 0.1 ha)	2	5

2.2.4 Crop Yield Estimation Service

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Crop yield estimation	4	5
Crop quality estimation	2	5
Crop residues estimation	3	5
Crop Yield Estimation service (Level of detail: Parcel Level)	5	5
Crop Yield Estimation service (Level of detail: Management Zones)	3	5
Crop Yield Estimation service (Level of detail: 0.1 ha)	2	5

2.3 APOLLO platform auxiliary services

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Alerts from the APOLLO platform via SMS, email and APOLLO app push notifications	5	5
Choose the kind of alerts that wants to receive	3	5
Allow other APOLLO platform users to receive alerts regarding subscriber's farm	5	5
View data in form of maps, reports, statistics and charts	3	5
Access historical information about fields	4	5
Compare information regarding different time and location	3	5
Choose when to receive periodical information	3	5
Interact with other APOLLO users	5	5
Change the alert levels of the services	2	5
Create custom algorithms	2	5
Choose the desired spatial resolution	2	5

2.4 Subscription Policy

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Choose which service to use at any time	4	5
Pay on demand based on the number of services and the frequency of use	5	5
Pay on demand according to the period of use	5	5
Pay regarding the spatial resolution of the received information*	5	5
Trial period of use*	5	5
Pay according to choices*	5	5
Pay according to the area that receives information for	5	5

2.5 Shared Access to APOLLO platform

User Requirement	Incorporation in APOLLO platform versions after Users feedback Scale 1-5 (Very Low – Very High)	
	Farmers	Crop Consultants – AgriCooperatives
Allow access to other APOLLO platform users under conditions	5	5
Have access, under conditions, to more than one APOLLO platform users at the same time	2	5

3 Conclusions

This deliverable has detailed the user requirements of the APOLLO platform. APOLLO platform aims to provide a set of innovative services for small farmers and for agriculture stakeholders based on Earth Observation satellites data. User requirements were defined by following the human-centered design methodology proposed by Maguire and Bevan (2002) and Wieggers and Beatty (2013), and will be refined via forthcoming activities of the project and specifically from T2.2 (Service specifications) and T2.3 (Co-creation of services). The aforementioned approach, helped on defining the requirements that are close to the needs of the users.

The results were document in form of *Personas* and *Scenarios Of Use* for delivering a more comprehensive view by enhancing realism and for offering insights into the ways that the platform will be actually used.

This deliverable has confirmed the need for the APOLLO platform proposed services. Specifically, key stakeholders found very useful to have information related to tillage, irrigation, crop growth and yield estimation. In addition, stakeholders presented their need for additional services. Specifically, they expressed their demand for services such as weather monitoring and forecast, fertilization recommendation, pests and disease alerts and time of harvest.

Finally, many of them annotated that the information must be given in an easy and understandable way and expressed the opinion that they will pay for APOLLO platform only if the offered services are credible and the prices are reasonable.

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Annex II: Questionnaire for Farmers

APOLLO User Requirements Questionnaire for Farmers

The APOLLO project is conducting a survey in order to assess farmers' needs and requirements for developing the APOLLO Platform. The APOLLO platform will collect and analyse satellite data in order to offer added value services to small farmers, crop consultants and agricultural cooperatives. The services that will be offered are tillage scheduling service, irrigation scheduling service, crop growth monitoring service and yield estimation service, as described below.

Tillage Scheduling

The Tillage Scheduling service can provide information on soil tillage according to the soil's water content. The farmer can estimate if it is possible to apply soil tillage and to identify spots where the soil cannot be treated (e.g. mudding spots).

Soil degradation due to improper tillage at low soil moisture content

Tractor stuck in the mud due to high soil moisture content

Irrigation Scheduling

Irrigation Scheduling determines the correct frequency and duration of watering for avoiding problems caused to crops by over- and/or under-application of water.

Wilted crops due to absence of water

Over-irrigated crop

Crop Growth Monitoring Service

Crop Growth Monitoring is the process of monitoring the crop status from emergence to harvest. In this way, farmers can be early alerted on infestations and nutrient deficiencies.

Wheat with proper development

Wheat with fungal infestation

Yield Estimation Service

Crop yield estimation is the process of estimating crop yield parameters before harvest. Expected income and evaluation on crop and/or variety adaptability can be assessed.

Wheat yield and protein estimation maps

Q1	Questionnaire ID:	
Q2	Survey Date:	

DEMOGRAPHICS					
Q3	Area and country:				
Q4	What is your age group?				
	18-34 <input type="checkbox"/>	35-44 <input type="checkbox"/>	45-54 <input type="checkbox"/>	55-64 <input type="checkbox"/>	65+ <input type="checkbox"/>
Q5	What is your gender?				
	Male <input type="checkbox"/>			Female <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q6	What is your education level?				
	Primary <input type="checkbox"/>	Secondary <input type="checkbox"/>	Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Post Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	

GENERAL INFORMATION				
Q7	What kind of crops do you cultivate?			
	Arable Crops <input type="checkbox"/>	Orchards <input type="checkbox"/>	Open Field Vegetables <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q8	Which are the crops that you cultivate?			
	1.	2.	3.	
	4.	5.	6.	
Q9	What is the total area that you cultivate?			
	Less than 10 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	10-30 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	30-60 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	60-90 ha <input type="checkbox"/>
Q10	How would you prefer to access information via the internet?			
	Desktop PC <input type="checkbox"/>	Tablet <input type="checkbox"/>	Smartphone <input type="checkbox"/>	I don't connect to internet

				<input type="checkbox"/>
Q11	Are you familiar with the use of maps in applications such as Google Maps?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q12	How important do you think smart agriculture is?			
	Not Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Of Minor Importance <input type="checkbox"/>	Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Important <input type="checkbox"/>
Q13	How important do you think the incorporation of satellite data in agriculture is?			
	Not Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Of Minor Importance <input type="checkbox"/>	Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Important <input type="checkbox"/>
Q14	Do you use any smart farming technologies (software, hardware)?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q15	If yes, which product(s)/service(s) do you use?			
Q16	What type of device(s) do you use with them?			
Q17	Which are the reason(s) for using them?			

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APOLLO SERVICES DEVELOPMENT						
Q18	What information would interest you most in a tillage scheduling service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Tillage Scheduling Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Soil Moisture Variation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Soil Workability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q19	What information would interest you most in an irrigation scheduling service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Irrigation Scheduling Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Soil Moisture Variation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Time of Irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Amount of Irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Evapotranspiration Variation Variation in the amount of moisture lost through evaporation and plant transpiration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q20	What information would interest you most in a crop growth monitoring service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Crop Growth Monitoring Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Crop Stage <small>Stage of growth in the crop's phenological cycle</small>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Crop Vigor Variation <small>Variation in the health of the crop</small>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Leaf Area Variation <small>Variation in the quantity of overall leaf surface</small>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Biomass Variation <small>Variation in the quantity of plant matter</small>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q21	What information would interest you most in a yield estimation service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Yield Estimation Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5

	Estimated Crop Yield	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Estimated Residue Yield	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Estimated Crop Quality	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>					

APOLLO PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT						
Q22	What type of alerts would you like to receive from the APOLLO services?					
	SMS <input type="checkbox"/>	Email <input type="checkbox"/>	APOLLO app Push Notifications <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q23	How would you prefer to receive information from APOLLO platform?					
	Directly <input type="checkbox"/>			Through an agricultural consultant <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q24	Please rate the following ways of displaying the information from the APOLLO platform from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important.					
	Information presented as:	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Maps	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Statistics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Charts	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q25	In what file type(s) should the results be exported (e.g. CSV, SHAPEFILE, TEXT)?					

Q26	Would you like to be able to access historical information about your fields?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q27	How often would you like to receive information?				
	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Biweekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>
Q28	Would you like to interact with other farmers using the APOLLO platform?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q29	Would you like to interact with crop consultants using the APOLLO platform?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q30	Would you like to be able to change the alert levels according to your needs?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q31	Why would you like to be able to change the alert levels according to your needs?				
Q32	Would you be willing to pay for APOLLO services?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, but only if <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q33	What would your preferred payment model be?				

	Monthly subscription covering all services <input type="checkbox"/>	Annual subscription covering all services <input type="checkbox"/>	On demand, based on which services I use, and how much I use them <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q34	Would you like to have a choice regarding the services you would use within the platform?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q35	Knowing that a proper field variability management can increase profitability, would you like to have field management zones information?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q36	What type of granularity would you prefer for the services' results?			
	Per field <input type="checkbox"/>	Per Management Zone <input type="checkbox"/>	Per 1 ha <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Per 0.1 ha <input type="checkbox"/>
Q37	Would you like to have the ability to create custom algorithms on top of the APOLLO platform?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q38	Why would you like to have the ability to create custom algorithms on top of the APOLLO platform?			
Q39	How are these services going to best complement your existing method of crop cultivation?			

Thank you for your time!

APOLLO services will be available to selected users on a free trial basis starting from Spring 2017. Would you like to be included as a trial user?	
Yes, I would like to take part in a free trial of the APOLLO services <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Annex III: Questionnaire for Crop Consultants

APOLLO User Requirements Questionnaire for Crop Consultants

The APOLLO project is conducting a survey in order to assess crop consultants' needs and requirements for developing the APOLLO Platform. The APOLLO platform will collect and analyse satellite data in order to offer added value services to small farmers, crop consultants and agricultural cooperatives. The services that will be offered are tillage scheduling service, irrigation scheduling service, crop growth monitoring service and yield estimation service, as described below.

The Tillage Scheduling service can provide information on soil tillage according to the soil's water content. The farmer can estimate if it is possible to apply soil tillage and to identify spots where the soil cannot be treated (e.g. mudding spots).

Tillage Scheduling

Soil degradation due to improper tillage at low soil moisture content

Tractor stuck in the mud due to high soil moisture content

Irrigation Scheduling determines the correct frequency and duration of watering for avoiding problems caused to crops by over- and/or under-application of water.

Irrigation Scheduling

Wilted crops due to absence of water

Over-irrigated crop

Crop Growth Monitoring is the process of monitoring the crop status from emergence to harvest. In this way, farmers can be early alerted on infestations and nutrient deficiencies.

Crop Growth Monitoring Service

Wheat with proper development

Wheat with fungal infestation

Crop yield estimation is the process of estimating crop yield parameters before harvest. Expected income and evaluation on crop and/or variety adaptability can be assessed.

Yield Estimation Service

Wheat yield and protein estimation maps

Q1	Questionnaire ID:	
Q2	Survey Date:	

DEMOGRAPHICS					
Q3	Area and country:				
Q4	What is your age group?				
	18-34 <input type="checkbox"/>	35-44 <input type="checkbox"/>	45-54 <input type="checkbox"/>	55-64 <input type="checkbox"/>	65+ <input type="checkbox"/>
Q5	What is your gender?				
	Male <input type="checkbox"/>			Female <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q6	What is your education level?				
	Primary <input type="checkbox"/>	Secondary <input type="checkbox"/>	Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Post Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	

GENERAL INFORMATION				
Q7	For what kind of crops do you provide advisory services?			
	Arable Crops <input type="checkbox"/>	Orchards <input type="checkbox"/>	Open Field Vegetables <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q8	For which crops do you provide advisory services?			
	1.	2.	3.	
	4.	5.	6.	
	7.	8.	9.	
Q9	What is the total area for which you provide advisory services?			
	Less than 100 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	100-300 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	300-600 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	600-900 ha <input type="checkbox"/>
Q10	How many farmers do you consult?			

Q11	How would you prefer to access information via the internet?			
	Desktop PC <input type="checkbox"/>	Tablet <input type="checkbox"/>	Smartphone <input type="checkbox"/>	I don't connect to internet <input type="checkbox"/>
Q12	Are you familiar with the use of maps in applications such as Google Maps?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q13	How important do you think smart agriculture is?			
	Not Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Of Minor Importance <input type="checkbox"/>	Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Important <input type="checkbox"/>
Q14	How important do you think the incorporation of satellite data in agriculture is?			
	Not Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Of Minor Importance <input type="checkbox"/>	Important <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Important <input type="checkbox"/>
Q15	What type of services do you provide to your clients?			
Q16	Do you use any smart farming technologies (software, hardware) for your advisory services?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q17	If yes, which product(s)/service(s) do you use?			

Q18	What type of device(s) do you use with them?
Q19	Which are your reason(s) for using them?

APOLLO SERVICES DEVELOPMENT						
Q20	What information would interest you most in a tillage scheduling service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Tillage Scheduling Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Soil Moisture Variation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Soil Workability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q21	What information would interest you most in an irrigation scheduling service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)						
	Irrigation Scheduling Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5	
	Soil Moisture Variation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Time of Irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Amount of Irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Evapotranspiration Variation Variation in the amount of moisture lost through evaporation and plant transpiration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Q22	What information would interest you most in a crop growth monitoring service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)						
	Crop Growth Monitoring Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5	
	Crop Stage Stage of growth in the crop's phenological cycle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Crop Vigor Variation Variation in the health of the crop	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Leaf Area Variation Variation in the quantity of overall leaf surface	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

	Biomass Variation Variation in the quantity of plant matter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q23	What information would interest you most in a yield estimation service? (Please rate from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important)					
	Yield Estimation Aspects	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Estimated Crop Yield	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Estimated Residue Yield	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Estimated Crop Quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

APOLLO PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT						
Q24	What type of alerts would you like to receive from the APOLLO services?					
	SMS <input type="checkbox"/>	Email <input type="checkbox"/>	APOLLO app Push Notifications <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q25	Please rate the following ways of displaying the information from the APOLLO platform from 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 the most important.					
	Information presented as:	Not Important 1	2	3	4	Very Important 5
	Maps	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Statistics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Charts	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

					
Q26	In what file type(s) should the results be exported (e.g. CSV, SHAPEFILE, TEXT)?					
Q27	Would you like to be able to access historical information about your clients' fields?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q28	How often would you like to receive information?					
	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Biweekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q29	Would you like to interact with farmers using the APOLLO platform?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q30	Would you like to interact with other crop consultants using the APOLLO platform?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q31	Would you like to be able to change the alert levels according to your needs?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q32	Why would you like to be able to change the alert levels according to your needs?					
Q33	Would you be willing to pay for APOLLO services?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, but only if <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q34	What would your preferred payment model be?					
	Monthly subscription covering all services <input type="checkbox"/>	Annual subscription covering all services <input type="checkbox"/>			On demand, based on which services I use, and how much I use them	

					<input type="checkbox"/>
Q35	Would you like to have a choice regarding the services you would use within the platform?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q36	Knowing that a proper field variability management can increase profitability, would you like to have field management zone information for your clients?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q37	What type of granularity would you prefer for the services' results?				
	Per field <input type="checkbox"/>	Per Management Zone <input type="checkbox"/>	Per 1 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	Per 0.1 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>
Q38	Would you like to have the ability to create custom algorithms on top of the APOLLO platform?				
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q39	Why would you like to have the ability to create custom algorithms on top of the APOLLO platform?				
Q40	How are these services going to best complement your existing toolkit of services?				

Thank you for your time!

APOLLO services will be available to selected users on a free trial basis starting from Spring 2017. Would you like to be included as a trial user?

D2.1: Report on User Requirements

Yes, I would like to take part in a free trial of the APOLLO services <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
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A P O L L O

Annex IV: Focus Group Survey Guidelines

FOCUS GROUP Survey GUIDELINES

Participants

- 12 people will be called for the focus group survey (8 farmers, 2 crop consultants and 2 people from the administrative staff of the co-ops).
- The focus group must be formed by farmers and crop consultants with farmers being the majority.
- The focus group survey will be conducted by a moderator and his assistant.
- The moderator moderates the talking while the assistant moderator keeps written notes.
- Each person will be assigned with an id number for the analysis purposes.
- One person speaks at a time. Before he speaks he needs to tell his id number.
- Moderator and assistant moderator need to distribute the APOLLO SERVICES OVERVIEW.
- Before starting the survey participants need to fill the demographics questionnaire.

Environment

- You need to be comfortable. It is good to offer them biscuits/cakes and refreshments to feel more comfortable.
- You need to have circle seating.
- The focus group survey will take between **45 and 90 minutes.**
- **The FOCUS GROUP SURVEY must be TAPE RECORDED!!!**

MODERATOR SKILLS

- Listens attentively with sensitivity and empathy
- Is able to listen and think at the same time
- Believes that all group participants have something to offer no matter what their education, experience, or background
- Has adequate knowledge of the topic
- Can keep personal views and ego out of the facilitation
- Is someone the group can relate to but also give authority to
- Can appropriately manage challenging group dynamics

ASSISTANT MODERATOR SKILLS

- Runs a tape recorder (smartphone) during the session
- Take notes in case the recorder fails or the tape is inaudible
- Note/record body language or other subtle but relevant clues
- Allow the moderator to do all the talking during the group

Introduction

WELCOME

Thanks for agreeing to be part of the focus group. We appreciate your willingness to participate.

INTRODUCTIONS

Moderator; assistant moderator

PURPOSE OF THIS FOCUS GROUP

We have been asked by APOLLO CONSORTIUM to conduct the focus group survey.

The reason we are having these focus groups is to **DEFINE THE USER NEEDS FOR DEVELOPING AN EARTH OBSERVATION BASED ADVISORY PLATFORM FOR FARMERS**. APOLLO platform will collect and analyze satellite data in order to offer added value services to small farmers, crop consultants and agricultural cooperatives. The services that will be offered are tillage scheduling service, irrigation scheduling service, crop growth monitoring service and yield estimation service.

We need your input and we want from you to share your honest and open thoughts with us.

GROUND RULES

1. YOU ARE THE EXPERTS!!!

We want you to do the talking.

We would like everyone to participate.

I may call on you if I haven't heard from you in a while.

2. THERE ARE NO RIGHT OR WRONG ANSWERS

Every person's experiences and opinions are important.

Speak up whether you agree or disagree.

We want to hear a wide range of opinions.

You must listen respectfully as others share their views.

You will not interrupt the others during their talking.

3. WHAT IS SAID IN THIS ROOM STAYS HERE

We want folks to feel comfortable sharing when sensitive issues come up.

4. WE WILL BE TAPE RECORDING THE GROUP

We want to capture everything you have to say.

We don't identify anyone by name in our report. You will remain anonymous.

5. YOU NEED TO SAY YOUR ID NUMBER BEFORE SPEAKING.

This will help us in our statistical analysis. No one will be identified in our report.

6. WE ASK TO TURN OFF YOUR CELLPHONES DURING THIS SURVEY.

This will help us in having accurate tape transcript.

A FOCUS GROUP IS NOT:

A debate

Group therapy

A conflict resolution session

A problem solving session

An opportunity to collaborate

A promotional opportunity

An educational session

DEMOGRAPHICS

Area and Country:				
FOCUS GROUP ID NUMBER:				
What is your Age Group?				
18-34 <input type="checkbox"/>	35-44 <input type="checkbox"/>	45-54 <input type="checkbox"/>	55-64 <input type="checkbox"/>	65+ <input type="checkbox"/>
What is your Gender?				
Male <input type="checkbox"/>		Female <input type="checkbox"/>		
What is your Education Level?				
Primary <input type="checkbox"/>	Secondary <input type="checkbox"/>	Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Post Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	
What is your Job?				
Farmer <input type="checkbox"/>		Crop Consultant <input type="checkbox"/>		

INDICATIVE QUESTIONS TO BE ANSWERED DURING THE FOCUS GROUP

Topic 1: Crop Production Problems

What are the main problems that you face in a cultivating period for each crop type that you cultivate (e.g. tillage problems, irrigation problems, crop growth problems etc.). Be specific at your answers. What are the main problems that you face in a cultivation period?

Topic 2: Current Practices

How do you avoid/solve these problems today? Are the practices that you use efficient enough? Are you willing to change practices? Be specific at your answers.

Topic 3: Prospects from APOLLO platform

How do you believe that these solutions will help you to solve these problems? Are you going to have solutions for these problems in the near future? How do you believe that these solutions will help you at solving these problems? In which way do you believe that a satellite based advisory platform should help you? Be more specific at your answers. What kind of services would you like to receive from a platform like this? In which way do you want to communicate with other APOLLO users? (e.g. forum, Q/A, newsfeed, direct messages)

Topic 4: APOLLO platform implementation

How do you believe that these solutions should be implemented using new technologies (smartphones, tablets, personal computers)? In what way do you envision the outputs of the platform (reports, maps, charts, tables)? What do you expect to see in a report? What is the information you want to see in APOLLO platform's starting page?

Topic 5: Frequency of information

How often do you believe that you are going to use the APOLLO platform per service? When do you need the information per operation? How often?

Topic 6: Communication of Information

Which device will help you most on getting information from the APOLLO platform? Which device you use most for getting and sharing information (desktop, tablet, smartphone)? What is your opinion on sharing the information/provide alerts with others? (e.g. agronomists, sub-contractors, other)

Topic 7: Market Infiltration

How do you believe that you should be convinced for using these solutions? What are the main criteria that you will depend upon for choosing the platform? How can we help you adopt (believe in) this platform? What should be the cost of these services? How would you like to pay for these services?

APOLLO SERVICES OVERVIEW

<h3>Tillage Scheduling Service</h3>	<p>Tractor stuck in the mud due to high soil moisture content.</p>	
	<p>Tillage scheduling service can provide information on soil tillage according to soil's water content. The farmer can estimate if it is possible to apply soil tillage and to identify spots where the soil cannot be treated (e.g. mudding spots).</p>	
<h3>Irrigation Scheduling Service</h3>	<p>Over-irrigated crop.</p>	
	<p>Irrigation is the artificial application of water to the land or soil. Irrigation scheduling determines the correct frequency and duration of watering for avoiding problems caused to crops by over- and/or under- application of water.</p>	
<h3>Crop Growth Monitoring Service</h3>	<p>Wheat with fungal infestation.</p>	
	<p>Crop growth monitoring is the process of monitoring the crop status from emergence to harvest. In this way, farmers can be early alerted on infestations and nutrient deficiencies.</p>	
<h3>Yield Estimation Service</h3>	<p>Wheat yield and protein estimation maps.</p>	
	<p>Crop yield estimation is the process of estimating crop yield parameters before harvest. Expected income and evaluation on crop and/or variety adaptability can be assessed.</p>	

END OF DOCUMENT

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